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Research Article

**DESIGN, FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF
ISAVUCONAZOLE BUCCAL TABLETS**Yerrolu Swetha*¹, L. Satyanarayana¹¹Department of pharmaceutics, Omega college of pharmacy, Osmania University, Telangana, India.**Article Received: September 2024 Accepted: October 2024 Published: November 2024****Abstract:**

Objective: Isavuconazole is an Antifungal drug used to treat invasive fungal infections. it has oral bioavailability (98%) and half-life 130 hr. It is administered through the buccal mucosa enters directly in the systemic circulation, thereby minimizing the first pass hepatic metabolism and adverse gastro-intestinal effects. Therefore, the present investigation is concerned with the development of the buccal tablets.

Methods: The present work was performed to develop and evaluate buccal tablet containing anti-fungal drug (Isavuconazole). Guar gum was used as bucco adhesive polymer. Thickness, hardness, weight variation and drug uniformity were investigated.

Results: The tablet formulations were also subjected to drug release in 900 ml 6.8 phosphate buffer. Ex vivo bioadhesion, was determined. F6 formulations showed maximum amounts of drugs release (99.12%) at the end of 10 hrs dissolution study. F6 also showed maximum bioadhesion (0.276 N).

Conclusion: The results of the study suggested that new buccal tablet formulations of guar gum bucco adhesive polymer can be suitably developed as an alternate to conventional dosage forms.

Keywords: Isavuconazole, Buccal tablet, Ex vivo bioadhesion, Guar gum.

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INTRODUCTION:

The mouth is lined with mucous membrane and among the least known of its functions is its capability of serving as a site for the absorption of drugs [1]. In general, drugs penetrate the mucous membrane by simple diffusion and are carried in the blood, which is richly supplied with the salivary glands and their ducts, into the systemic circulation via the jugular vein. Active transport, pinocytosis and passage through aqueous pores usually play only insignificant roles in moving drugs across the oral mucosa [2].

Isavuconazole is anti-fungal medication used to treat invasive fungal infections including invasive aspergillosis and mucormycosis, fusariosis, scedosporiasis [3]. It is an alternative to patient who can't tolerate voriconazole. It has biological half-life of 130hrs, and usual initial dose is 200 mg each 8hours thrice daily for 2 days, followed by maintenance dose of 200mg daily [4].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Isavuconazole pure drug was obtained as a gift sample from Hetero drugs, Hyderabad, India. hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) K4M, PVP K30, magnesium stearate, ethyl cellulose, guar gum, mannitol, and talc from SD fine chemicals, Hyderabad, India.

Determination of λ_{max} of Isavuconazole in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 solution:

Isavuconazole was carefully weighed, dissolved in sufficient volume of phosphate buffer pH 6.8. The standard stock solution of isavuconazole and 0.1 N HCL was serially diluted and was scanned in the 200-400nm range against buffer as a control solution. Isavuconazole's max spectra was observed at wavelength of 262 nm.

Primary Stock Solution (1mg/ml) :

100 mg of Isavuconazole pure sample was dissolved in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and made up to 100 ml in volumetric flask.

Working Stock solution (100 μ g/ml) :

5 ml of stock solution was dissolved in 50 ml

phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and make up the volume to 50 ml measuring flask. Aliquots of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1 and 1.2 ml of working stock solution were pipette out right into 10ml volumetric jars. The quantity was made up to the mark with phosphate buffer pH 6.8. This offers serial concentrations of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 μ g/ml of Isavuconazole. The absorbance was assessed with the help of UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 262nm utilizing phosphate buffer pH 6.8 as blank and a graph of concentration Vs absorbance was plotted.

Preparation of buccal tablets:

Isavuconazole buccal tablets were prepared employing a direct compression technique using HPMC K4M, Ethyl-cellulose, and Guar-gum as mucoadhesive polymers.

Method:

All the ingredients including medicine, polymers and excipients were weighed as per the set formula shown in Table 1. The drug is thoroughly mixed with mannitol on a butter paper with the assistance of a stainless-steel spatula. Then, all the components except lubricants were mixed in the order of increasing weights and blended for 10 minutes in an inflated polyethylene pouch. After homogeneous blending of ingredients, lubricant was added and again mixed for 2 minutes. The prepared blend of each preparation was pre-compressed [5] on 10-station rotary tablet punching machine at a low compression force to form single layered flat-faced tablet of 9 mm diameter, and final compression was done at a high compression force. The prepared tablets are given in Figure 1.

Analysis of Precompression Parameters:

The following precompression variables like P^H , Angle of repose, bulk density, Tapped density, Carr's Index, Hausner's Ratio were evaluated as per standard procedure [6].

Compatibility of excipients:

Fourier transform infrared (IR) spectroscopy was utilized to describe the possible interactions between the drug and the polymers in the solid state on shimadzu spectrum by the conventional KBr pellet method. The spectra were scanned over a frequency range 4000-400/cm [7].

Table:1 Isavuconazole buccal mucoadhesive tablets in various formulation

Ingredients (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Isouvcnazole	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
HPMC K4M	-	-	-	-	-		15	30	45
Ethyl cellulose,	15	30	45	-	-	-	-	-	-
Guargum	-	-	-	15	30	45	-	-	-
Mannitol	89	74	59	89	74	59	89	74	59
PVP K30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
Magnesium stearate	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Talc	3	333	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Total	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

PVP: Polyvinylpyrrolidone, HPMC: Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose

Fig. 1 Mucoadhesive Buccal tablets of Isavuconazole**Evaluation of buccal tablet:**

Twenty tablets were selected at accidental and weigh up individually. The individual weights were compared with the average weight for determination of weight variation, thickness, hardness and friability of the tablets were determined by using Monsanto hardness tester and Roche friabilator respectively [8].

Uniformity of drug content:

Accurately weighed quantity of the powder tablet equivalent to 50 mg of the drug was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask. 40 ml of distilled water was added, mix with the help of mechanical gyratory shaker for 10 minutes, and then the volume was made up to 100 ml with the distilled water, mixed solution was filtered through the membrane filter disc with an

average pore diameter not $>0.45 \mu\text{m}$. A volume of 5 ml of the filtrate was diluted to 100 ml with water and absorbance was measured at 262 nm against clear water under ultraviolet spectrophotometer [9].

Assessment of surface pH:

The surface pH of the formulated Isouvcnazole buccal tablets was determined to evaluate the probable irritation effects on the mucosa. The buccal tablets were placed in glass tubes and allowed to swell in contact with distilled water (12 ml) for 2hrs at room temperature and the pH was measured by keeping the cathode of the pH meter the surface of the tablet and permitting it to equilibrate for 1 minute [10].

Swelling index:

Agar (5% w/v) was dissolved in hot water, transferred into petri plates and allowed to solidify. Six Isouvonazole buccal tablets from each batch were placed in a vacuum overnight prior to the study to remove the moisture if any and tablet's initial weight was calculated, placed in a Petri dish with 6 ml of phosphate buffer at pH 6.8

and fermented at 37°C. The tablet was withdrawn, sealed in channel paper. At the end of the test, buccal tablets were reweighed at distinct periods i.e 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, and 08 hr and the percentage moisture absorption was calculated using the following formula [11].

$$\% \text{Moisture Absorption} = \frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

Fig. 2 Swelling of Isouvonazole Buccal Tablets

Mucoadhesive strength:

A transformed physical balance was used for measuring the mucoadhesive strength. The left pan was removed. The buccal tablet was then stuck to glass stopper through its assistance membrane using an adhesive (Feviquick). To left arm of the balance the glass stopper along with the tablet was hanged. A clean glass mortar was placed below hanging glass stopper. The balance was so adjusted that right hand-side was exactly 5 g heavier than the left. Fresh sheep buccal mucosa was obtained from a nearby butcher home and used within 2 hrs of butcherer. The mucosal membrane was separated by removing the underlying fat and loose tissues, washed with distilled water and then with phosphate buffer pH 6.8 at 37°C. The fresh sheep buccal mucosa was cut into pieces and washed with phosphate buffer pH 6.8. A piece of buccal mucosa was tied firmly with the mucosal side upwards by

utilizing string over the hollow 50 ml glass cylinder, the cylinder was used because it was giving strength to the buccal mucosa, and it was not float during the adhesion. The cylinder was then embedded into the 500ml glass beaker filled with phosphate buffer pH 6.8 kept at 37±0.5°C to keep mucosal membrane wet. This was then kept below the left-hand setup of the balance. The tablet to be tested for bio adhesion was then stuck with a little moisture. The 5 g mass on the right pan was removed. This lowered the tablet over the mucosa, with a force of 5 g. The balance was kept in this position for 3 minutes, and then the weight was increased gradually to the right hand pan till the tablet detached from the mucosal surface (Fig. 1). The detachments force gave the bio adhesive strength of the buccal tablet in gram [12,13]. From the mucoadhesive strength, force of adhesion and then the averages of three determinations were calculated.

$$\text{Force of Adhesion (N)} = (W \times g)/1000$$

$$\text{Bond Strength (N/m)} = \text{Force of Adhesion} / \text{Surface Area.}$$

Fig.3 Determination of Mucoadhesive strength of Isouvcnazole

***In vitro* drug release study:**

The experiment was carried out in a USP Tablet Dissolution Test Device II equipped with a paddle stirrer turning at 50 revolutions per minute and 900ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 as the medium. The released study was performed at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The backing layer of the buccal tablet is attached to glass disk with cyanoacrylate adhesive. The disk is placed at the bottom of the dissolution vessel. At predetermined time intervals, five millilitres of

test medium were withheld and replaced with fresh medium. The samples were filtered through $0.45\mu\text{m}$ membrane filter disc (Millipore Corporation) and analysed for Isouvcnazole after appropriate dilution by measuring the absorbance at 262 nm with a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The experiment was run in triplicate¹⁴. The dissolution data was examined to determine the actual sum of sedative discharge and the percentage of cumulative drug release at various time intervals.

Fig. 4 Determination of *In vitro* drug release study of Isouvcnazole

Stability studies:

Stability is identified as the measurement of capabilities of formulation to stay inside its physical, chemical, corrective, and toxicological decision.

These studies were conducted for all the formulations at $37^\circ \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and 75% RH to investigate the effect of temperature on the drug content in different film formulations. The films were removed from the oven

at the end of 0th day, the first week, the second week, 3rd week, and one month and they were analysed for drug content. Average of triplicate readings was taken [15].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The main goal of this work was to develop new mucoadhesive buccal tablets of Isavuconazole, is anti-fungal consisting of drug free non-adhesive

protective layer. The Absorption-maxima (λ_{max}) of Isavuconazole was obtained at 262nm. The calibration curve of drug was achieved over the concentration range of the 2.5-15 μ g/ml. A linear correlation was attained between the quantity of Isavuconazole (μ g/ml) & absorbance. The linearity data is given in Table 2 and standard calibration curve of Isavuconazole is shown in Fig5.

Table: 2 Linearity data of Isavuconazole

S. No	Concentration (μ g/ml)	Absorbance
1	2	0.198
2	4	0.343
3	6	0.479
4	8	0.622
5	10	0.778
6	12	0.931

Fig. 5 Calibration curve of Isavuconazole

The purity of the drug sample was identified by scanning the drug sample on IR spectrophotometer. The peaks of the IR spectra of drug sample were found to be comparable with the standard IR spectra of pure Isavuconazole as reported. Fig. 6 shows the IR spectra of Isavuconazole. The IR spectra of the blend of drug and polymer indicated no incompatibility was observed between drug and polymers in Fig.7. Hence HPMC K4M, guar gum and ethyl cellulose were chosen as polymers for further investigations. The spectrum of drug shows absorption bands at S=O intensifying (1079 cm⁻¹),

tertiary amine (3094 cm⁻¹), C-- N enhancing (1296 cm⁻¹, 1233cm⁻¹), C-S broadening (634 cm⁻¹), N-- H broadening (3376 cm⁻¹).

The evaluated precompression parameters results of nine formulations are summarized in Table 3. The double layered structure design was expected to provide drug delivery in a unidirectional fashion to the mucosa and to avoid loss of drug due to wash out by saliva, release drug immediately to produce a prompt pharmacological action and remain in oral cavity and provide a sustained release of enough drug

over an extended period. A total of nine formulations of mucoadhesive buccal tablets of Isouconazole were prepared and evaluated for biological, physical and mechanical parameters. The hardness of prepared buccal tablets of nicorandil was found to be 4.450.5 to 4.960.2 kg/cm². Mean thickness and weights were found to be uniform as indicated by the low values of standard deviation. The thickness and weight variation of the formulated buccal tablets were found to be in the range of 3.35 to 3.42 mm and 147.24 to 154.26 mg respectively. Friability values 0.38 to 0.57 % indicate good mechanical strength to bear the troubles of handling and transportation. Results are given in Table 3. The drug content of buccal tablets was quite uniform as seen in Table 3. The average drug content of the buccal tablets was found to be within the range of 98.231 and 102.651% and the low values of standard deviation and coefficient of variation (<2) indicate uniform distribution of the drug within the prepared buccal tablets. The surface pH was determined to investigate the possibility of any side-effects in the oral cavity as acidic or alkaline pH is bound to cause irritation to the buccal mucosa. Surface pH of all formulations was found to be almost in neutral pH and ranged between 5.19 and 6.78 and no mucosal irritation was expected. The surface pH of all the formulations is shown in Table 4. The swelling index of mucoadhesive tablets is shown in Table 4. Among all the formulations, F8 having polymer of HPMC K4M showed maximum swelling index of 69.3% after 8th and followed by F2, F3, F7, F1, F6, F4, F5 and F9. From the swelling index results, as given in Table 4, it was concluded that swelling increases as the time proceeds because the polymer gradually absorbs water due to the hydrophilicity of the polymer. The farthest

hydrophilic polymer gets hydrated, which results in swelling and a gel barrier is formed at the outer surface. As the gelatinous layer progressively dissolves or disperses. The swelling nature supports an idea viewing the moisture intake capacities of polymers and the alterations in swelling of the hydrophilic polymers may be due to the difference in resistance of the matrix network structure. The bio adhesion strength of Isouconazole buccal tablets is shown in Table 5. Adhesion occurs shortly after the beginning of swelling, but the bond formed between mucosal layer and polymer is not very strong. The adhesion will increase with the degree of hydration until a point where over-hydration leads to an abrupt drop in adhesive strength due to disentanglement at the polymer/tissue interface. The formulation F6 showed maximum muco adhesion strength and residence time. The mucoadhesive strength of the formulation F6 was found to be maximum of 0.276 ± 0.06 . The cumulative % drug release of all formulation for 10hrs is given in Table 6 and the graph was shown in Fig.8. Among all the nine formulations, F6 was found to be the highest percentage drug release. During the study, it was observed that the tablets were initially swollen and not erodible over the period of 10 hrs. It was concluded that by increasing the concentration of guar gum in the formulation, the drug release speed from the tablets was found to be increased. This may be due to increased hydration (or) swelling characteristics of polymer with increased concentrations. From the overall data, it was found that the formulation F6 showed the maximum percentage of drug release, i.e. 99.12% at the end of 10hrs.

Table: 3 Evaluation of pre-compression parameters of Isavuconazole muco-adhesive matrix tablets F1- F9

Formulation No	Bulk density (gm/cc)	Tapped density (gm/cc)	Angle of repose (Θ)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio
F1	0.285± 0.03	0.329± 0.02	18.45±0.07	11.63±0.04	1.12±0.05
F2	0.269± 0.02	0.350± 0.04	25.47±0.07	23.13±0.02	1.34±0.02
F3	0.274± 0.02	0.348± 0.02	21.31±0.02	20.33±0.02	1.26±0.02
F4	0.296± 0.03	0.355± 0.02	21.44±0.02	19.49±0.04	1.27±0.05
F5	0.250± 0.02	0.328± 0.04	22.19±0.02	16.72±0.02	1.28±0.02
F6	0.271± 0.03	0.326± 0.02	20.21±0.07	18.13±0.04	1.13±0.02
F7	0.288± 0.02	0.392± 0.02	21.65±0.02	18.65±0.02	1.28±0.05
F8	0.284± 0.02	0.388± 0.04	22.38±0.02	19.12±0.02	1.26±0.02
F9	0.291± 0.03	0.396± 0.02	20.54±0.07	19.43±0.04	1.32±0.05

Fig. 6 Fourier transform infrared spectrum of Isavuconazole pure drug

Fig. 7 Fourier transform infrared spectrum showing Isavuconazole compatibility with excipients Table:3

Table: 4 Evaluation of post-compression parameters of muco-adhesive matrix tablets F1- F9

Formulation No	Hardness (kg/Cm ³)	Weight variation(mg)	Friability (%w/w)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content uniformity (%)
F1	4.45±0.02	151 ±0.02	0.53±0.03	3.36±0.02	99.43±0.04
F2	4.46±0.04	154 ±0.05	0.46 ±0.02	3.32±0.02	98.28±0.02
F3	4.57±0.02	149 ±0.02	0.41 ±0.03	3.35±0.02	102.4±0.02
F4	4.53±0.04	145 ±0.02	0.56 ±0.02	3.32±0.02	99.14±0.04
F5	4.66±0.02	155 ±0.05	0.37 ±0.03	3.39±0.02	98.45±0.02
F6	4.75±0.02	154 ±0.02	0.44 ±0.02	3.30±0.02	99.62±0.02
F7	4.78±0.02	156 ±0.02	0.43 ±0.02	3.42±0.02	99.54±0.04
F8	4.84±0.04	146 ±0.05	0.46 ±0.03	3.33±0.02	99.56±0.02
F9	4.96±0.02	147 ±0.02	0.45 ±0.02	3.34±0.02	99.58±0.04

Table: 5 physicochemical properties of Buccal tablets formulations F1- F9

Formulation No	Surface P ^H N=3	Bio adhesive strength(N)	%Swelling after 8hrs
F1	6.07±0.03	0.226 ±0.06	61.3
F2	6.19±0.02	0.184 ±0.06	68
F3	6.17±0.03	0.256 ±0.06	68
F4	6.32±0.02	0.223 ±0.06	58.6
F5	6.37±0.02	0.255 ±0.06	58
F6	6.32±0.03	0.276 ±0.06	60
F7	6.12±0.02	0.258 ±0.06	62
F8	6.26±0.03	0.263 ±0.06	69.3
F9	6.03±0.02	0.267 ±0.06	56.6

The values are expressed in SD±; SD= Standard deviation

Table: 6 Cumulative % *in-vitro* drug release studies of mucoadhesive tablet formulations F1 – F9

Time (Hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1	9.15	10.82	7.84	10.38	11.04	11.83	7.82	9.56	8.75
2	16.55	22.24	16.56	18.27	18.25	18.64	17.55	18.35	14.32
3	28.88	30.37	24.28	27.16	26.96	29.72	23.28	27.23	23.44
4	37.45	37.46	35.74	39.83	34.86	36.47	37.74	34.37	33.23
5	45.87	46.57	44.28	48.14	42.84	45.75	45.28	42.82	44.23
6	58.75	57.72	57.16	60.02	55.45	57.82	58.16	58.45	54.34
7	64.24	69.26	65.27	68.93	68.58	69.96	66.27	64.27	66.33
8	76.56	73.18	76.96	79.51	72.94	76.03	77.96	77.46	72.56
9	84.27	84.42	86.43	89.63	84.25	89.42	87.43	85.22	84.12
10	90.82	96.89	94.65	98.14	97.71	99.12	95.65	93.12	93.11

Fig. 8 Cumulative percentage drug release of formulations from-F1-to-F9

CONCLUSION:

The mucoadhesive strength was influenced by the nature and proportion of the mucoadhesive polymer used in the formulations. In all the formulations, three types of mucoadhesive polymers are used in different concentrations, among those the Guar gum, HPMC K4M have shown good mucoadhesive strength. Buccal tablets formulated (F6) with Guar gum showed comparatively higher bio adhesion than that of all other formulations. Very strong mucoadhesion could damage the epithelial lining of the buccal mucosa. Mucoadhesive strength exhibited by the formulation F6 tablets can be considered satisfactory for maintaining them in the oral cavity for 12 hrs. The surface pH was determined to investigate the possibility of any side effects, in the oral cavity. The surface pH of the buccal tablets depends on the nature and composition of mucoadhesive polymers. Surface pH of F6 formulation was found 6.32. This pH is near to the neutral, so the buccal tablet does not cause any irritation on the mucosa. The *ex vivo* residence time was determined by using modified physical balance method. Formulations F6 showed higher bio adhesive time when compared to the other formulations. This test reflects the mucoadhesive capacity of polymers used in formulations. The results revealed that Guar

gum containing formulations showed better bio adhesion than all other mucoadhesive polymer in the formulations. Based on *ex vivo* mucoadhesion, and *in-vitro* release studies formulation F6 was selected.

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